

Effect of Activity-Based Approach on Performance in Basic Science Concepts among Lower Basic Students in Soba Educational Zone, Kaduna State

Yunusa, Idris¹

Iyunusaidris2020@gmail.com

09012283751

Sirajo, Ibrahim¹

Sirajoibrahim56@gmail.com

08060661774

Ibrahim, I. Madinat²

Madinat01ibrahim@gmail.com

08024422275

¹Integrated Science Department, School of Secondary Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gusau

²Biology Department, School of Secondary Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gusau

Abstract

The study investigated the effect of activity-based approach on performance in Basic Science concepts among lower basic students in Soba Educational Zone, Kaduna state. The design of the study is quasi-experimental involving pretest and posttest experimental and control groups. The population comprised of all Basic Science students at the lower level in the study area. A sample size of 200(100 Male and 100 Female) lower Basic Science (JSS II) students in the 2023/2024 academic session was arrived using multi stage sampling technique randomly selected in two schools using table of random number with equal gender 100 each. One of the schools was assigned as experimental and the other as control using simple random sampling technique having 50 male and 50 female each. The instrument used for the study was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) adopted from Usman (2000) with a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.86$. The results obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistic in answering the research questions and t-test statistic for testing the hypotheses at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance which revealed a significant difference between those students in the experimental group taught using activity instructional approach and those using conventional method in the control and also the activity-based method was found to be gender friendly, that is, both male and female students benefitted equally when taught with the instructional approach. In conclusion, the study showed that Basic Science students at lower level achieved significantly higher when they are taught some Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach but no difference in performance among gender. From these findings, some recommendations were made among which training of Soba local government Basic Science teachers on innovative and students-centered approach should be given a paramount consideration.

Keywords: Activity-Based Approach, Basic Science and Academic Performance

Introduction

One of the objectives of National Policy on Education (FME, 2005) is to equip students to live effectively in modern age of science and technology. In line with this objective, science subjects are among the core subjects that are being taught in secondary schools and also in Nigeria colleges of education, polytechnics and universities. At the junior secondary school level integrated science presently called Basic Science was introduced for the purpose of giving solid foundation for subsequent science studies at the higher level (Usman, 2000).

Basic Science was introduced into Nigerian secondary schools in 1972 at the junior secondary school level. The course objectives of the Basic Science programme were clearly spelt out. These objectives are still difficult to achieve due to so many factors, such as teacher related factors, attitude of teachers and students toward Basic Science, use of inappropriate teaching strategy, lack of use of instructional materials, as well as misconception about Basic Science as subject itself, which unified all the science disciplines in terms of concept, themes, philosophy methodology and evaluation among others.

Various studies have shown that teachers of Basic Science are not qualified and this in turn affects academic performance (Usman, 2007). Out of the major problems of the teachers is that inability to use appropriate activity-based teaching strategy they often used traditional lectures that led to the poor academic performance in junior secondary schools in Basic Science (Odetoyinbo, 2004 and Usman 2007).

Various actively-based teaching strategies have been employed for the purpose of improving the teaching and learning of Basic Science at junior secondary school level. These are, inquiry method, demonstration, process approach, cooperate learning, laboratory activity method and Nigerian Integrated Science Teacher Education Project (NISTEP). (Mari,1992 and Usman, 2007). These teaching strategies usually took place within the class room environment but in Basic Science course of junior secondary school projects book three (STAN, 1989) there are some units which demand the use of inside classroom and outside classroom investigations in form of indoor and outdoor environment. The various studies cited the teaching strategy employed by teachers is limited to the indoor laboratory investigations. The aspect of the outdoor laboratory activities is often neglected, or in some cases converted to the traditional lecture method as observed by Stanley (2008) and Duniya (2009). Stanley (2008) and Duniya (2009) claimed that the activity method for teaching biology concepts was due to the facts that the outdoor demands the students to handle, observe and collect -on the -spot information of a particular concept unlike the indoor in which the materials are brought to the classroom for students to observe and make investigations within the limited classroom environment.

On the issue of gender, Usman (2007) found out from their various studies that boys perform well in any 'rigorous' work, while girls show to settle seated for less rigorous work. Bichi (2008) believed that girls perform better than boys in problem solving type of activities. In another dimension, if boys and girls are given the equal opportunities. They will perform equally well (Yoloye,2004 and Nworgu,2005). The issue of gender in science teaching seems to be a controversial. In this study therefore there is need, to investigate the issue of gender difference on performance in Basic Science using activity approach at the junior secondary school to find out if is gender friendly.

Various studies revealed that the major problem of teaching and learning Basic Science more especially at junior secondary school level among others is the lack of competent and trained Basic Science teachers, in-ability to effectively use innovative teaching techniques and the constant use of conventional teaching method which is teacher-centred but neglect the use of students-centred approaches, hence account for poor performance among the students. This poor performance persists as a result of constant use of the conventional method of teaching (Usman (2000), Stanley (2000). Thus, there is need to provide an alternative teaching strategy which will suit the demand of Basic Science course content at the junior secondary school level such as activity-based teaching approach. It is on this background the study was conducted to investigate the effect of Activity-Based teaching approach on the academic performance among lower level of Basic Science students of Soba Education Zone, Kaduna state.

Objectives of the study

The study has among others the following objectives which are to:

1. Determine the effects of activity-based teaching approach on academic performance among lower Basic Science students of Soba Education Zone.
2. Investigate the effect of activity-based teaching approach on academic performance between male and female Basic Science students in the zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores of Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional approach and their counterparts who were taught same concepts using conventional method?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female Basic Science students taught using the activity-based teaching strategy?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were stated for testing at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach and those taught using conventional method of instruction.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based approach in Soba Educational Zone.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental study involving pretest and posttest design was used in the study. The two groups were given pretest and the results showing that the groups were equivalent in their ability level. Group A assigned as experimental group which were exposed to activity-based instructional strategy while group B as control group exposed to conventional method of instruction. The instrument used was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) adopted from Usman (2000). It was made up of 20 multiple choice items validated by experts with reliability of co-efficient of 0.86. The maximum obtainable score is 20 one mark each was allocated for a correct response. The treatment of the study involves teaching the subjects some Basic Science concepts for the period of 4 weeks for each group. After the treatment administration a posttest was administrated. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistic for answering research questions and t-test statistics at $p < 0.05$ for testing the stated hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

The results are hereby presented through the following:

Research Question One:

What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores of Basic Science students taught using activity-based instructional teaching strategy and those taught same concepts using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean Scores of the Academic Performance of Basic Science Students in the Experimental Group taught using Activity-Based Instructional Approach and those in the Control taught using Conventional Method.

Group	N	Mean score (\bar{x})	SD	S.E	Mean Gain
Experimental	100	13.55	12.09	0.22	
Control	100	12.50	12.01	0.18	1.05

Table 1 revealed a mean performance score of 13.55 and 12.50 of Basic Science students in the experimental and control groups respectively and a mean difference of 1.05. It showed that students in the experimental group who were taught using activity-based method of instruction performed better than those in the control group who were taught using conventional method.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the academic performance mean scores between male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based teaching strategy?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Academic Performance between Male and Female Basic Science Students in the Experimental Group taught using Activity-Based Instructional Approach.

Group	N	Mean score (\bar{x})	SD	S.E	Mean Gain
Male	50	13.25	12.41	1.62	
Female	50	13.20	12.39	1.60	0.05

Table 2 revealed a mean academic performance scores of 13.25 for the male Basic Science students and that of female student's is 13.20. The results indicated an insignificant mean difference or gain of 0.05 implying that both girls and boys students performed equally as they were taught the Basic Science concepts using the activity instructional approach.

Hypothesis 1

Results of the data analysis were presented in tables 3 and 4 with the stated hypotheses as follows:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the academic performance mean scores between the Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based method of instruction in the experimental group and their counterparts taught using conventional method.

Table3: t-test Analysis of Academic Performance of Basic Science Students of the Experimental group taught using Activity-Based Approach and those taught using Conventional Method in the and Control group.

Group	n	Mean score(\bar{x})	S.D	SE	Df	P-val	RM
-------	---	-------------------------	-----	----	----	-------	----

Experimental	100	13.55	12.09	0.22			
					198	0.001	Sign
Control	100	12.50	12.01	0.18			

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The result in Table 3 showed ap-value of 0.001 at the degree of freedom of 198. The critical p-value of 0.001 is less than the p-value of $p \leq 0.05$. This shows that there was significant difference in the academic performance between Basic Science students who were taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional strategy and those students taught using the conventional method of teaching. Thus, the null hypothesis, which says there is no significant difference is hereby rejected. Hence there was significant difference in favour of the students taught using the activity-based approach.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using activity-based instructional strategy

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Academic Performance between male and female Basic Science students taught using Activity-Based Method of Instruction.

	n	Mean score (\bar{x})	S.D	SE	df	p-val	Remark
Experimental	50	13.25	12.41	1.62	98	0.07	Not Significant
Control	50	13.20	12.39	1.60			

Not significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 4 revealed a p-value of 0.07 at degree of freedom of 98 which is greater than p value of 0.05, hence implies that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based method, thus the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby retained. This means that the activity approach is achieved equally by both girls and boys in the process of teaching, hence it is gender friendly.

Discussion of Findings

From Tables 1 and 3, the findings of the study showed that there was significant difference between the academic performance of Basic Science students taught using activity-based method of teaching and those taught using the conventional method. The findings were in favour of the students who were taught using the activity instructional method. The findings is in agreement with that of Baker et al (2003) and Stanley (2008) who reported that innovative teaching method such as activity is more effective that the conventional teaching method in science. The superiority of the approach has been attributed to the opportunity of the students exposed to the variety of activities both indoor and outdoor engaged by themselves and to be able to collect specimens by themselves as well as making use of their mental process during on –the – spot in data collection unlike for conventional lesson are provided in the classroom.

Table 2 of the research question and that of Table 4 of the hypothesis testing revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Basic Science students taught Basic Science concepts using the activity-based teaching strategy. The findings are in agreement with those of Yoloye (2004) and Nworgu (2005) that if boys and girls are given equal opportunity will perform equally well. The findings showed that activity-based instructional approach is gender friendly. It is suitable for both boys and girls Basic Science students at junior secondary school level. The lack of significant difference could not be by chance, because the activity allows students despite their gender differences to collect data and make an on-the-spot observation, analyze and report their findings. According to Duniya (2009) when students are exposed to outdoor activity, they will be able to make significant investigations which are important aspect of learning influence. In this study male and female students were given equal opportunity by learning themselves using the varieties of activities.

Conclusion

The Activity-based instructional method used in this study enhanced the academic performance of student in Basic Science at junior secondary school level. The activity instructional method was also found to be gender friendly. It enhances the academic performance of students despite their gender differences.

Recommendations

1. Science teachers should be trained on the effective use of innovative and students-centered strategies such as the Activity Approach through series of workshops.
2. The use of activities should not be allowed to extinct; teachers should endeavor to use it more often during teaching situations in science education particularly Basic Science and Technology at lower level.
3. Textbook publishers, including STAN, should incorporate more activities that will warrant the use of activity in their publications.
4. Federal, State, Soba Local Government and NGOs as well as parents should assist in the procurement of necessary instructional materials that will lead to effective use of activities in Basic Science and Technology subjects.

References

- Bakers, S. Slings, D. And Tilling S (2003): Teaching Biology outside the Classroom is it Heading for Extinction? FSC Occasion at Publication 72 British Ecology Sociology.
- Bichi, S.S (2008) Effects of Gender on Historically Enriched Curriculum on Academic Achievement in Evolution Concept among Senior Secondary Students of Published Seminar Paper Science Education Department of Education A.B.U Zaria.
- Duniya, J.N. (2009) Efficacy of Indoor and Outdoor Laboratory Approaches on Acquisition of Science Process Skills, and Performance Among Biology, Polytechnics Students' Seminar Paper Presented In Science Education Department of Education A.B.U Zaria, Nigeria.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2005), National policy on Education N.E.R.D.C, Press Yaba, Lagos Nigeria.
- Haruna, M. (2008) Comparative Study of the effectiveness of indoor and outdoor teaching techniques on senior secondary school performance in chemistry in annual Emirate, Jigawa state. A seminar paper presented, Department of education ABU Zaria.
- Mari,J.S. (1994) The Understanding of Science Process and its Relationship to Achievements in Integrated Science on unpublished Med Thesis Department of Education A.B.U Zaria.
- Nworgu, I.N. (2005) Effects of Gender Sensitization Packaged on Students Achievement in Integrated Science *Journal Of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria* 40(1&2)74- 78.
- Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (1989) *Nigeria Integrated Science Project*. Heinemann Educational Book III Nigeria Limited.
- Stanley,M. (2008) Indoor and Outdoor Laboratory Experiences on Secondary School Students Academic Achievement and Retention in Ecology in Kaduna State Unpublished Med Thesis, Department of Education A.B.U Zaria.
- Usamn I.A. (2000). The Relationship Between Students Performances in Practical Activities And Their Academic Achievement In Integrated Science. NISTEP Mode of Teaching Unpublished PhD Thesis Department of Education, A.B.U Zaria.
- Usman I.A. (2007) Relationship Between Students Performances in Practical Activity and Their Academic Achievement in Senior Secondary School Biology Using NISTEP Mode of Teaching. *Journal of Educational Research and Development* 2(3)240-244
- Yoloye, T.W. (2004). *That We May Learn Better: An Inaugural Lectures Delivered at the University of Ibadan*. Ibadan University Press Ibadan Nigeria.